

The Monastic School of Gaza

By Lampros Alexopoulos, University of Thessaloniki

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The Monastic School of Gaza was a monastic intellectual community flourished in the region of Gaza toward the end of the fourth century and in the first half of the fifth. It produced a wealth of literary works, such as monastic instructions, historical and hagiographic treatises, letters etc., and exhibited some of the most prominent figures of Eastern Christian monasticism. This monastic community is depicted as a “school” due to the fact that the central figures of Gazan monasticism displayed an intense interest in pedagogy, mainly in the ethical formation of the monks. The spiritual exercises, the moral progress and didactic methods reflect sustained at the monasteries reflect a pedagogic practice that bear close resemblance to training in the philosophical schools of Greco-Roman antiquity. There were several significant historical events in Egypt that led to the establishment and the intellectual blossoming of monasticism at Gaza, which soon became the stronghold of anti-Chalcedonian resistance in Palestine. More specifically, at the end of the fourth century, the Origenist controversy caused turbulence to Egyptian desert monasticism. Monks that were suspected as adherents of Origenistic views and beliefs were persecuted. Several of the monks that fled the area known as Scetis (the region of Wadi El Natrun, Arabic for “Natron Valley”, a valley located in Beheira Governorate, Egypt) found refuge in the Gaza area. In addition, during the first half of the fifth century, the invasion of the Mazices, tribes of Berbers of North Africa, reduced the numbers of the monks at the monastic center at Scetis. Many of these monks wandered beyond the Egyptian border and ended up in the Gaza area. Two are the claimants to the title of the founder of Palestinian monasticism: Chariton and Hilarion. Chariton, originating from Iconium in Asia Minor, came to the Judean Desert at the beginning of the fourth century and died in the laura at Faran, near Jerusalem, in the middle of the same century. According to St. Jerome, however, who traveled in the area at the end of the fourth century, it was Hilarion the one who introduced monasticism to Palestine. Hilarion was born around 291/2 in the village of Thabatha, south of Gaza, and died in Cyprus in 371. Another prominent figure of the Monastic School of Gaza was Abba Isaiah, an Egyptian monk who began his monastic life in a coenobium and later secluded himself in the desert. He drew many admirers, and in order to avoid them he decided to emigrate to Palestine. He finally withdrew to the Gaza region, in the second half of the fifth century, most probably near Beth Dallatha, in an effort to escape the hordes of admirers who congregated at his door seeking assistance and spiritual direction. Abba Isaiah introduced a significant shift in Gaza monasticism, revolutionizing its patterns of leadership and affecting every aspects of its life. In the years after the Council of Chalcedon (451) he established a coenobium that incorporated forms of lauritic monasticism and forged a pattern of spiritual leadership that continued in the first half of the sixth century among the monastic circle of Gaza under Barsanuphius and John. Abba Isaiah became one of the leaders of the anti-Chalcedonian opposition in Palestine. He died in his monastery in 491. During the same time, Peter the Iberian, an Iberian prince and former political hostage at the royal court of Constantinople, founded his monastery at Bethlehem (430). Consecrated as bishop of Maiuma in 452, he escaped to Egypt due to a decree of a local ruler that banished all the anti-Chalcedonian bishops. In the early 470s, Peter moved to Palestine where he continued ascetic activities, acquiring great fame as a holy Father. The appointment of Peter’s disciple, Severus, as Patriarch of Antioch, marked the end of the anti-Chalcedonian monastic center of Gaza. Until that time, a fairly extensive network of anti-Chalcedonian monasteries existed in the area, extending northward toward Caesarea from the region to the south and east of Gaza, including the enclave of the Eleutheropolis area, which apparently constituted the geographic base for the anti-Chalcedonian resistance in Palestine. Anti-Chalcedonian monasteries also existed in Maiuma, Caphar She’artha, Migdal Thabatha, Kanopis, Beth Dallatha, Gerar and Peleia near Ascalon. But the rise of the Chalcedonian emperor Justin (518) and his nephew Justinian and the changing

politico-ecclesiastical climate led to the expulsion of anti-Chalcedonian bishops and monks from the region. Hence, the stage of the next generation of Gaza monasticism became Thabatha. There, at the first half of the sixth century, Barsanuphius and John, their disciple Dorotheus of Gaza and Abba Seridus, had their monastery. This community accepted the Council of Chalcedon, at least externally, and apparently preferred to withdraw into monastic piety. With the Islamic conquest, the historical sources fell silent and the monastic community of Gaza sank into oblivion.

Date Range: 320 CE - 536 CE

Region: Gaza.

Region tags: Middle East, Eastern Mediterranean, Israel, Gaza

Palestine region, mid. 4th century.

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite
- ✓ Religious Specialists
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: John Chryssavgis and Pachomios (Robert) Penkett, "Abba Isaiah of Scetis Ascetic Discourses", Translated, with an Introduction and Notes, Cistercian Publication, Kalamazoo, Michigan 2002.
- Source 2: Derwas J. Chitty, "Barsanuphius and John, Questions and Answers", PO 31/3, Paris, 1966.
- Source 3: Eric P. Wheeler, "Dorotheos of Gaza: Discourses and Sayings", Cistercian Publications, Kalamazoo, 1977.

Notes: -Severus of Antioch, Letters, Syriac text and Eng. trans., E. W. Brooks, PO 12/2, 1916. -F. J. Hamilton and E. W. Brooks, "The Syriac Chronicle Known as That of Zacharia of Mytilene", London, 1899. -Lena Ambjrn, "The Life of Severus by Zachariah of Mytilene", Gorgias Pr Llc, 2008. -Sebastian Brock-Brian Fitzgerald, "Two Early Lives of Severos, Patriarch of Antioch", Translated with an introduction and notes, Liverpool, Liverpool University Press, 2013.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://gedsh.bethmardutho.org/Isaiah-of-Scetis>
- Source 1 Description: Isaiah of Scetis, Gorgias Encyclopedic Dictionary of the Syriac Heritage: Electronic Edition
- Source 2 URL: <https://citydesert.wordpress.com/2015/01/20/the-asceticon-of-abba-isaiah-of-scetes/>
- Source 2 Description: The "Asceticon" of Abba Isaiah of Scetes
- Source 3 URL: <https://thicketandthorp.com/2018/04/14/questions-and-answers-with-the-elders-of-gaza/>
- Source 3 Description: Questions and Answers with the Elders of Gaza

Notes: -http://www.copticplace.com/Saints_E/Lives_of_Saints/Barsanuphius.html Sts. Barsanuphius and John -https://www.taize.fr/en_article5234.html Dorotheus of Gaza (Sixth Century) Humility and Communion -<https://www.britannica.com/biography/Severus-of-Antioch> Severus of Antioch

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: https://www.tertullian.org/fathers/severus_coll_1_intro.htm

– Source 1 Description: Severus of Antioch: A collection of letters from numerous Syriac manuscripts.

– Source 2 URL: <https://www.tertullian.org/fathers/zachariah00.htm>

– Source 2 Description: Zachariah of Mitylene, Syriac Chronicle.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: Before its Christianization, Gaza was a famous pagan stronghold. Mark the Deacon provides us a with very vivid description of the city of Gaza at the end of the 4th century, when Porphyry arrived as its new bishop: on the arrival of Porphyry, the pagan population of the city, who had gladly accepted the Julian's policy for the restoration of the pagan religion, threw thorns from the palms instead of flowers, while they burned cow dung instead of incense. Nevertheless, only a few years after Porphyry's entrance, in 402, by order of the emperor, all the pagan temples of Gaza were demolished. Idols or pagan books were confiscated and burnt, eventually leading to the burning of Marneion, the temple of Gaza's city god, Marnas. As far as theological issues are concerned, the monk Nephalius, a supporter of the doctrine of Chalcedon, persecuted anti-Chalcedonians and tried to oust all of the anti-Chalcedonian monks from their monasteries in the region and supplant them with Chalcedonians. These efforts disturbed the atmosphere of coexistence between Monophysites and Chalcedonians in the region.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: It is significant to note that Hilarion was sent from Constantinople with an edict ordering the closing of the pagan temples, but he left untouched the secret performance of rites in the Marneion, having been bribed by the devotees. Furthermore, it is witnessed that the pagans and the Christians lived peacefully and cooperated in various matters concerning the region. Chalcedonian monasticism coexisted in the region alongside its anti-Chalcedonian counterpart, though it may have maintained a low profile during the period of Monophysite monastic authority.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: There were violent conflicts, which included military intervention, only during the Christianization of Gaza in the early 5th century. These conflicts led to the destruction of pagan temples, such as the Marneion. As far as theological disputes are concerned, there was no violence per se. However, there were times when anti-Chalcedonians were persecuted and punished with exile and/or excommunication.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: Not exactly. The assignment of religious affiliation in the case of the monastic school of Gaza was between Chalcedonian and Non-Chalcedonian Christianity. The first, accepted the theological and ecclesiological resolutions of the Council of Chalcedon held in 451 and its Definition, which repudiated the notion of a single nature in Christ, and declared that he has two natures in one person and hypostasis. It also insisted on the completeness of his two natures: Godhead and manhood. The second, did not. It is worth to note, nevertheless, that Peter the Iberian requested devotion to the Monophysite faith and denial of the Council of Chalcedon from his disciples.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: In fact, there were various periods in which political power favored one religious group or the other, i.e. the Chalcedonians and the anti-Chalcedonians. The emperor Zeno (488), tried to convince Abbah Isaiah and Peter the Iberian (both of them anti-Chalcedonian leaders) to support the conciliatory policy of his "Henotikon", a christological document that aimed to reconcile the differences between the supporters of the Council of Chalcedon and the council's opponents. Both Isaiah and Peter avoided making the voyage. This latter, in fact, was a protégé of the empress Eudocia, wife of the emperor Theodosius II. Eudocia also provided the land for the foundation of an anti-Chalcedonian monastery west of Eleutheropolis. A political climate favorable to the anti-Chalcedonians existed under the rule of the emperor Anastasius, from 491 to 518, which led to the restoration of the anti-Chalcedonian monasteries. However, after Anastasius's death, his successor Justin and his nephew Justinian led to the expulsion of anti-Chalcedonian Palestinian abbots and monks to Egypt.

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– No

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– No

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– Yes

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– No

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Yes

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: Not as such. In fact, one of the problems connected with apostasy that the adherents of the religious group in question faced, was their attitude to the holy places. The attachment of anti-Chalcedonians to holy places, pilgrimage sites or monasteries under Chalcedonian domination implied collaboration and communion with the archenemy of the true faith—Monophysitism. Thus, the sincere anti-Chalcedonian living in the holy places had to make the bitter choice either to abandon his attachment to and veneration of the holy places, thereby remaining true to his faith and brethren, or to retain communion with the “heretical” Chalcedonians.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (seen as being part of a related larger religious group)

– Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: The monastic community developed in the region of Gaza was deeply versed in previous ascetic literature, such as the rich Pachomian and Evagrius corpora, the Sayings of the Desert Fathers (Apophthegmata Patrum), and the ascetical writings of Basil. This literature was considered authoritative and contained everything a monk needed to achieve the purpose of his monastic life, as well as answers and instructions for practical questions of everyday life. Thus, Peter the Iberian encouraged the monks of his monastery to read continuously Basil's ascetic writings, and advocated a monastic life led according to Basil's teachings and rule, since his book was written by the inspiration of divine grace and the Holy Spirit. Furthermore, Barsanuphius and John's main sources of inspiration were the Bible, Abba Isaiah, the “Apophthegmata”, Evagrius, and Basil of Caesarea, and their spiritual direction consisted primarily of an intensive interpretation and application of these writings.

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Notes: In fact, a detailed description of the construction of a typical coenobium is preserved in the Life of Peter the Iberian: "First, he built the tower, and the church within it, and a chapel in the church. He built the wall of the monastery all round: and he established many cells, both lower and upper, and porticoes and pillars. He built a wall around the courtyard and dug a well and planted a garden. He looked after the rest of the needs and the building of the monastery and the manual labor of the brethren." Apparently this type of construction was typical and somewhat standard for all the monasteries in the region of Gaza.

Is iconography present:

– Field doesn't know

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: Jerusalem with its holy sites was a renowned pilgrimage site during the period under investigation. Furthermore, Transjordan and Mount Nebo were also famous as pilgrimage sites. There were many monks that visited these pilgrimage sites before they reside at one of the monasteries of the Gaza region. The most prominent pilgrim among the central figures of the monastic school of Gaza was Peter the Iberian. He founded a monastery in Jerusalem near the Tower of David that served in part as a pilgrim's hostel.

How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (common)

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Field doesn't know

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:
– Field doesn't know

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Notes: It should be noted an incident after Peter the Iberian's death: his heirs hastened to bury him in the old monastery near Maiuma, for fear that the people of Maiuma and Gaza would try to steal the body and inter it in one of their churches, a common phenomenon following the death of a saint. Peter's disciples and local Samaritan residents accompanied the coffin for quite a distance on its way to Maiuma. His body was laid in a sarcophagus alongside that of his friend John the Eunuch.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:
– No

↳ In cemetery:
– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– Field doesn't know

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: One of the most important and distinctive features, prevalent in monastic culture of Coptic monasticism, was the ideal of *xeniteia*. This is defined as a life of self-imposed exile, voluntary alienation and wandering, separation from family and detachment from all social relationships. This ideal aims at spiritual progress. The very essence of *xeniteia* is the perception of the monk as stranger, in both a physical and a spiritual sense. However, albeit there was a negative attitude toward itinerant monks that manifested a radical form of the ideal of *xeniteia*, leading to its perception as a source of trouble and a burden on the monastic community and associated with social disturbance, Peter the Iberian embraced this concept in an effort to end his life as a “stranger” to this world.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– No

↳ Courage (generic):

– No

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– No

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Cooperation:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– No

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– No

↳ Strength (physical):

– No

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes [specify]: The most vital virtue of coenobitic life was that of obedience.

Notes: The ideal of absolute obedience to a spiritual father was a key concept for Gazan monasticism. Obedience was considered to be the outstanding principle of coenobitic monasticism, and the leading figures of the Monastic school of Gaza organized life around it. They demanded, through their writings and their admonitions, annihilation of the monk's own free will. Discipline and obedience to the abbot left no room for spontaneous devotional behavior, while the monks' obedience to the abbot's instructions was strictly supervised. In fact, so strict was the rule of obedience that the monks not only avoided any unnecessary speech, but were even careful not to disclose their troublesome thoughts through their appearance, their gait, or the look in their eyes.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: One of Dorotheus of Gaza's key instructions to the monks was the renunciation of marriage. In fact, monastic conditions did not necessarily imply a total segregation from women. Many monks had opportunities to associate with women while performing errands for the monastery as well as when pious women visited the monastery, something that Abba Isaiah noticed, urging the ascetics to deal with these borderline situations and define the line of demarcation in monk-woman relations. Barsanuphius and John, on the other hand, claimed that perfect ascetics were empowered to overcome the various passions, emphasizing that they alone had the power to overcome sexual impulses entirely. Success in doing so was regarded as the crowning victory over the passions and a preparatory stage in the attainment of deification. The perfect ascetic was immune to even the stimulation caused by the erotic images in dreams. He was immune from even those stimulations considered natural and not demonic. He had suppressed them; he had become a spiritual eunuch.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: It requires full sexual abstinence.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: Abstinence from food and fasting are a central component in the life of a monk and its significance in a monastic setting is greatly magnified. A description of the daily life in the monastery near Maiuma comes from Zacharias the Rhetor, biographer of Severus. He depicts monks spent all their time fasting, standing throughout the day, holding vigils throughout the night, and praying ceaselessly, in private and public prayer. However, Barsanuphius refused to provide his disciples a rule for fasting because he thought that it would be useless and easily transgressed. Rather, he claimed,

each person needs a different rule according to his state of being and specific circumstances.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: One of Abba Isaiah's recommendations was that the monks should eat one meal a day. The golden rule was to stop eating while still hungry, while the quantity of wine was up to three glasses daily. Similarly, Barsanuphius and John held that one should always remain a little hungry and thirsty, albeit they acknowledged that the proper amount of food differs from one person to another and can only be learned from personal experience. Hence, it should be adjusted to the individual. Furthermore, they also held that meditation, suppressing the appetite, offers a means of coping with the difficulty of maintaining a strict dietary regime. Suppression of appetite through meditation was considered as a means of acquiring spiritual food that deflects the conscious need for material food.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: Dorotheus of Gaza instructed the monks to completely abandon any property they had, since even minimal relations of ownership and property could generate quarrels among the monks.

↳ To other in-group members:

– No

↳ To out-groups:

– No

↳ Destroyed:

– No

↳ Other:

– Yes [specify]: Charity

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: That depends on the rule of each monastic community.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

- ↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:
- Field doesn't know
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):
- Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.
- Field doesn't know

- ↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
- Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.
- No

- ↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
- Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.
- No

- ↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:
- No

- ↳ Is there use of intoxicants:
- No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

- No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

- No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose

one):

– An empire

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Notes: Although a portion of the donations given at the Gazan monasteries was distributed among the poor, famine relief or similar actions were not institutionalized. However the Gazan monasteries did provided the means to assist the poor and the needy. In fact, when Peter the Iberian left Constantinople, where he was held as a political prisoner, he had a considerable sum of money with him. He distributed this money mostly to the monks and the poor, the rest apparently being spent on the monastery, converted now to a hostel for the pilgrims, where they housed and fed pilgrims at their own expense. So did John, who instructed that poor people coming to the monastery to seek welfare should be treated with generosity. His disciple, after all, Dorotheus of Gaza, was responsible for his monastery's hostel.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: Although a portion of the donations given at the Gazan monasteries was distributed among the poor, poverty relief or similar actions were not institutionalized. However the Gazan monasteries did provided the means to assist the poor and the needy.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Notes: Dorotheus, the most famous disciple of Barsanuphius and John, was asked by them to establish and run a clinic in the monastery, in which he was aided financially by his brother, who was sympathetic to the monastic way. It is worth to mention that Barsanuphius and John were imbued, through divine intimacy, with spiritual and healing powers. However, these powers were channeled not through acts of direct miraculous intervention but through prayers, blessings, as a virtual substitute for amulets, and physical contact with objects belonging to the sick. They received requests for prayers on behalf of the sick, and their prayers are documented as having been effective.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: This monastic community is depicted as a “school” due to the fact that the central figures of Gazan monasticism displayed an intense interest in pedagogy, mainly in the ethical formation of the monks. The spiritual exercises, the moral progress and didactic methods sustained at the monasteries reflect a pedagogic practice that bear close resemblance to training in the philosophical schools of Greco-Roman antiquity. There was, therefore, within this monastic community a teacher and his disciples. Furthermore, daily life in the coenobium was structured by regular oral instruction and individual study. A sort of curriculum was implemented in order to habituate his brothers to ascetic virtues and imparted formal knowledge as the theoretical foundation of the set of virtues that would lead to the union with God. Hence, that kind of teaching in Gazan monasteries, both in content and methods, followed in the footsteps of classical education, albeit the Abba (abbot) could derive most of these elements from earlier Christian thinkers, such as Basil of Caesarea, Evagrius of Pontus etc.

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– Yes

Is such education open to both males and females:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: The monks actually devoted a small part of each day to manual labor, through which they met all their corporal needs. Furthermore, there are some rules regarding the property that a monk could own, i.e. monks who worked in agriculture could own a single work animal, such as a donkey, or a pair of oxen for ploughing the field

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

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